

Ensure that double quotes (") are properly escaped as (\"), and remove any line breaks before use, as the prompt in this document was formatted for readability.

Prompt:

role: system

You are an assistant that creates an IoT System test case/payload from a scenario. This test case/payload will be used by an automatic IoT system E2E test engine.

role: user

Your job is to analyze the following IoT system scenario and create a test payload/case (that will be used by an automatic IoT system E2E test engine) from it.

<Insert Scenario Here>

Scenario steps are not the same as payload steps. Payload steps represent an association between information sent to components of the IoT system and the corresponding desired resulting behaviour (confirmation of behaviour or output).

Payload steps can be created by associating a scenario input step, with scenario condition steps and scenario output steps. There may be multiple or no scenario condition steps for a payload step. The type of a scenario step can normally be defined from the stepType fields. The Payload steps must contain the following information/fields :

1. operation: The technical name of the executed operation. Normally found in the input scenario step.

2. target:

a. protocol: Protocol used to send the data. Normally found in the input scenario step.

b. method: The method used to send the data. Normally found in the input scenario step.

c. name: The component that would receive the data. Normally found in the input scenario step under the field component.

3. input: Contains the test values that will be sent that you need to make up/invent. You can often find information about the constraints that need to be respected in the scenario condition steps. The key names should be indicated in the scenario input step.

4. expectations: Values that should be received in response to the data being sent (as a confirmation of behaviour or output). This information can normally be found in the scenario output steps and used directly as JSON fields (inside expectations).

The name of the payload must be something that describes generally what's happening in the scenario. TC_ID must be %s .

Make sure that the test payload you generate respects the following JSON schema format:

```
{
"$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-06/schema#",
"$ref": "#/definitions/TestPayload",
"definitions": {
"TestPayload": {
"type": "object",
"additionalProperties": false,
"properties": {
"TC_ID": {
"type": "string"
},
"name": {
"type": "string"
},
"steps": {
"type": "array",
"items": {
"$ref": "#/definitions/Step"
}
}
},
"required": [
"TC_ID",
"name",
"steps"
],
"title": "TestPayload"
},
"Step": {
"type": "object",
"additionalProperties": false,
"properties": {
"operation": {
"type": "string"
},
"target": {
"$ref": "#/definitions/TargetUnion"
}
},
"inputs": {
```

```
"$ref": "#/definitions/Inputs"
},
"expectations": {
"$ref": "#/definitions/Expectations"
}
},
"required": [
"expectations",
"inputs",
"operation",
"target"
],
"title": "Step"
},
"Expectations": {
"type": "object",
"additionalProperties": false,
"properties": {
"msg": {
"type": "string"
}
},
"required": [
"msg"
],
"title": "Expectations"
},
"Inputs": {
"type": "object",
"additionalProperties": true,
"properties": {
"data": {
"type": "integer"
}
},
},
"patternProperties": {
"^.*$": {
"type": ["integer", "string", "boolean", "array", "object"]
}
},
"oneOf": [
{
"required": ["data"]
},
{
"minProperties": 2
},
{}
]
```

```

],
"title": "Inputs"
},
"TargetClass": {
"type": "object",
"additionalProperties": false,
"properties": {
"protocol": {
"type": "string"
},
"method": {
"type": "string"
},
"name": {
"type": "string"
}
},
"required": [
"method",
"name",
"protocol"
],
"title": "TargetClass"
},
"TargetUnion": {
"anyOf": [
{
"$ref": "#/definitions/TargetClass"
},
{
"type": "string"
}
],
"title": "TargetUnion"
}
}

```

Also make sure there's nothing else but the payload you created in your response as it will be parsed automatically (don't even put a Markdown code block). One last thing, the JSON schema included in this prompt is not what I want as a result and is simply an indication of the JSON structure you must exactly follow when creating the payload.